

LINGUISTIC PECULIARITIES OF PROVERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation. A proverb is a form of saying that offers guidance, is simply true, or has any other enduring lesson. A proverb is a short, well-known remark that people use to convey their feelings. More can be said in a proverb than in a thousand words. With the help of these proverbs, morality, truth, wisdom, friendship, loyalty, and other virtues are exalted. The similarities between English and Uzbek proverbs from a cultural and linguistic standpoint are discussed in this article.

Keywords: Proverb, saying, folklore, matal, antonym, zarbulmasal, and regional proverb.

Introduction. Proverbs can be used both literally and figuratively in written and spoken language. Some proverbs are exclusively used in figurative (e.g., "Crows do not pick crow's eyes," "An empty hand is no lure for a hawk," or "Ona yurting omon bo'lsa, rangiro'ying somon bo'lmas" ("If your nation prospers, you prosper")) or literal sense (e.g., "If your country prospers, you flourish"). The themes used in proverbs are numerous and varied. Proverbs can be found on a variety of subjects, including motherland, labor, knowledge, skill, friendship, unity, wisdom, vigilance, language and speech culture, love, bad traits, and more.^[1]

Proverbs typically have a dialectic unity of content and form, occasionally are rhyme-rich, occasionally have many interpretations, and oftentimes are metaphorical. Such a situation is sometimes found as an antithesis in proverbs, such as "Kattaga hurmatda bol, kichikka izzatda" ("Respect the older, respect the younger"). Proverbs can also be straightforward and written in verse. Proverbs like "Mehnat, mehnatning tagi rohat" ("Work is done, time for fun") are often written in prose, yet there are still lyrical patterns to be found there. Moreover, proverbs like "There are inner motifs and rhymes in proverbs, much like in poems." "ellar silar boshingni, lga bersang oshingni. Giving food to the people would earn you a pat on the head, according to the proverb Itga bersang oshingni. Dogs will nibble on your head if you give them your meal". The first collection of Turkic proverb examples may be found in Mahmud al-book

¹ Arora Sh. L. The perception of proverbiality. - New York: Garland Publishing Inc., 1994.

Kashgari's "Diwanu-Lugat al-Turk." Several of these proverbs, which have numerous variations, are still in use among Uzbeks.

For instance, the adage "Kishi olasi ichtin, qilqi olasi tashtin" ("Human's malice is hidden inside, in animals – outside"), which was given by Mahmud al-Kashgari, is currently used in the form "Odam olasi ichida, mol olasi tashida." The word "proverb" (maqol) is sometimes replaced with other words in Uzbek. They include terms like "masal," "zarbulmasal," "naql," "hikmat," "hikmatli soz," "tanbeh," "mashoyikhlari so'zi," "hikmatli maqol," "donishmandlar so'zi," and "otalar so'zi," among others. Proverbs generally have significant sociopolitical and educational importance. Several proverbs are popular among the populace, including "Qil uchida turibman" ("I hang in the balance," "Semizlinki qo'y ko'taradi" ("Fatness is the right fit for a ram"), "Tuyaga yantoq kerak bo'lsa, boynini cho'zar" ("If camel needs a bur, it stretches its neck"), "Bekorga mushuk oftobga chiqmaydi" ("Without reason, no cat comes out"). A proverb is a short phrase that conveys a truth or some practical knowledge.

Usually, it is based on experience or common sense. A proverb's purpose is to make the wisdom it conveys seem obvious. Many diverse cultures share the same saying. Real proverbs are adages that have been predominantly transmitted verbally from generation to generation. These might have even been recorded in writing. A proverb is a brief phrase that conveys a piece of universal knowledge. A proverb is a piece of wisdom that has been passed down from generation to generation. It explains events that have happened in the past and keep happening. Several proverbs kinds can be identified according to where they are found: Proverbs from different cultural backgrounds are often found to share the same underlying idea as well as the same or extremely similar wording. These proverbs are known as universal proverbs. Most of them are straightforward expressions of straightforward ethical ideas or straightforward observations, albeit not all straightforward expressions of straightforward observations have been translated into proverbs across all languages. Regional proverbs - Similar to how loan words are used, many loan proverbs are used alongside native ones in culturally connected locations.^[2]

A sizeable portion of them can be linked to the historical classical literature of the area, specifically the Sanskrit and Korean classics in the Far East and the Greco-Roman classics in Europe. Local Proverbs: Internal cultural

² Arewa O. and Alan D. Proverbs the Ethnography of Speaking Folklore. - American PublishingHouse, 1964.

divisions are common in a region, and not all languages hold the classics (such as the Bible or the Confucian Analects) in high regard as a source of proverbs. Another collection of typical regional proverbs is likewise influenced by geographic proximity. Several European and Far Eastern languages, including English and Korean, provide examples of these principles. Proverbs have traditionally been the most dynamic and reliable component of national languages, vying well with the aphorisms and sayings of great philosophers. The vividness of national thinking and its defining characteristics were represented in proverbs and sayings as well as in the imagery. Proverbs and sayings are a form of folklore that are concise but profound in its meaning. Under their social and ideal purposes, they convey the sentiment of the majority of people. Proverbs and sayings contain some specific aspects of historical evolution and human civilization. Proverbs can be classified into six categories: According to Meider W., proverbs can be categorized into six fundamental categories based on their meaning and purpose: A proverb called Synonym has two lines that, while they are stated slightly differently, ultimately say the same thing. E.G. Words are only leaves; deeds are fruits.

The term “antithetical” refers to an idea that is conveyed in the first line and it is the opposite articulated in the second. E.G. Actions are more powerful than words. Synthetics occurs when there is a common topic shared by two lines that appear to express completely different, even opposing, ideas. Integral occurs when the second line concludes the first line's notion. E.G. Don't bother worries till they bother you! When the first line exemplifies the second, we have a parabola. The second line serves as instruction, and the first is an analogy. E.G. Everything works out for the best. When a proverb compares one object to another to highlight a shared characteristic, it is considered comparative. E.G. Water is thinner than blood. Proverbs are thus a type of oral folk art. This proverb has a profound meaning and is short, metaphorical, and grammatically and logically complete. A precise, consistent, and commonly used rhythmic formula for proverbs originated from people's centuries-long experience. The reflection of people's views of life, attitudes toward society, history, spiritual condition, and positive attributes can be found in proverbs. Having been retained by the people for generations, they have a clear and straightforward lyrical structure.

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